

CHALLENGES IN THE ADVERTISING MARKET FOLLOWING META'S DEPARTURE FROM RUSSIA

Kostoreva A.

master, University of Georgia School of Law
USA

ABSTRACT

This article examines the challenges in the advertising market following Meta's departure from Russia. It highlights the significant shifts in company strategies, the transition to alternative platforms, and their impact on audience engagement. The adaptations of content and new challenges for marketers are discussed, along with the socio-economic consequences of these changes on the Russian market.

Keywords: advertising market, Meta departure, Russia, alternative platforms, content adaptation, socio-economic impact, marketing strategies.

Introduction

Internet advertising serves as a crucial tool for reaching a wide audience, increasing brand recognition, and promoting products or services among consumers. In the context of growing dependence on digital technologies and platforms, the departure of a major player such as Meta represents a significant event capable of radically altering the landscape of the advertising market.

The aim of this research is to analyze the challenges faced by advertising campaigns in connection with Meta's departure from Russia, as well as to explore alternative solutions for internet marketing. This includes examining how companies have adapted their advertising strategies to overcome new challenges and

assessing the impact of these changes on the overall Russian advertising market.

Main part

Meta Platforms, Inc., formerly known as Facebook Inc., stands as a pivotal entity within the digital landscape, orchestrating a suite of social networking sites and technological innovations that have redefined global communication, media distribution, and advertising strategies. The company's platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Messenger, have collectively amassed billions of active users, cementing Meta's role in the realm of internet advertising by offering unparalleled access to diverse and extensive audiences worldwide. Meta's annual advertising revenue increases annually (fig.1).

Figure 1. Annual advertising revenue of Meta Platforms worldwide, 2018-2023, million dollars [1]

The sustained growth can be attributed to a variety of factors, including the expanding digital economy, the efficacy of targeted advertising algorithms, and the broadening user base that engages with Meta's platforms. As of the end of 2020, that is, before leaving Russia, Meta's revenue in Russia amounted to 39.9 billion rubles, while the total volume of the Russian internet advertising market was 323 billion rubles [2].

The role of Meta social networks in the Russian advertising space before leaving

Meta's platforms, particularly Facebook and Instagram, were instrumental for Russian businesses in achieving extensive reach, engaging with target audiences, and conducting effective digital marketing campaigns [3]. These platforms offered advanced targeting

capabilities, allowing advertisers to tailor their messages to specific demographic, geographic, and psychographic profiles, thereby optimizing campaign performance and return on investment (ROI).

Meta's platforms were lauded for their innovative advertising solutions, including dynamic ads, video ads, and stories ads, which provided businesses with creative and interactive ways to showcase their products and services. These features were not only effective in capturing user attention but also in driving higher engagement rates and conversions.

According to Brand Analytics, Instagram ranked first in Russia in terms of active audience size in October 2021 (fig. 2), which had a direct impact on the internet advertising market [4].

Figure 2. Number of authors per month in 2021, in millions of people [4]

The departure of Meta from Russia has left a noticeable void in the digital advertising space, challenging businesses to find alternative platforms that offer comparable reach and sophistication in targeting and ad formats. This transition necessitates a strategic realignment, as companies are compelled to explore new digital landscapes and adapt their marketing strategies to maintain visibility and engagement with their target audiences.

The legal foundation for Meta's prohibition in Russia can be traced back to the country's stringent internet laws. A pivotal piece of legislation in this context is the law on «Information, Information Technologies, and Information Protection» [5].

This legislative framework set the stage for Meta's platforms to come under scrutiny, culminating in their designation as «extremist organizations» by Russian courts. The legal proceedings argued that Meta's failure to comply with requests to remove content considered as promoting extremism and violating national laws was a direct violation of the Russian internet regulation

laws [6]. Consequently, this led to the prohibition of Meta's operations within the country, marking a significant shift in the digital and social media landscape in Russia.

The impact of Meta's departure on advertisers and brands

Meta's withdrawal from the Russian market has forced advertisers and brands to critically review their brand promotion efforts. This withdrawal has left a significant void in the ecosystem, as Meta's platforms, particularly Facebook and Instagram, were previously instrumental for Russian businesses in terms of audience engagement and ad personalization capabilities [7].

The departure of Meta from the Russian market has necessitated a significant shift in digital advertising strategies among Russian companies. This transition is characterized by a move away from global platforms like Facebook and Instagram to more localized and alternative digital channels. The following table provides a comparative overview of the advertising landscape before and after Meta's exit.

Table 1.

Advertising strategies of Russian companies before and after Meta's exit from the market

Aspect	Pre-Meta exit	Post-Meta exit
Primary advertising platforms	Instagram, Facebook.	VKontakte (VK), Telegram, Yandex.Direct
Targeting capabilities	Advanced demographic and interest-based targeting	Diversified targeting including geolocation and behavioral insights
Engagement strategies	Influencer collaborations, stories ads, carousel ads	Influencer marketing, native VK ads, Video content
Audience reaches	Global and diverse	More localized and niche-focused
Measurement and analytics	Comprehensive insights on user engagement and conversion metrics [8]	Adapted analytics with a focus on local user behavior patterns
Outcomes	High engagement and conversion rates	Maintaining or improving engagement through localized strategies

After Meta left the Russian market, advertisers were forced to restructure their digital marketing towards alternative platforms aimed at local audiences. In this reshaped digital advertising landscape, VKontakte

(VK) and Telegram have emerged as the primary platforms for advertisers seeking to maintain their reach and engagement with Russian consumers (fig.3).

Figure 3. The number of people over the age of 12 who visited the site or the application at least once a month, million people [9]

VK, with its extensive user base and robust advertising tools, provides a familiar yet potent environment for targeted marketing campaigns, community building, and brand engagement. Similarly, Telegram has seen a surge in popularity as a versatile messaging app that offers unique opportunities for direct communication, content distribution, and channel-based advertising. These platforms' ascendancy reflects a strategic pivot among Russian advertisers, emphasizing the importance of adaptability and local focus in the face of global platform restrictions [10]. Through leveraging the distinctive features and audiences of VK and Telegram, advertisers continue to navigate the challenges of digital marketing in a post-Meta era, demonstrating resilience and innovation in their approach to reaching and engaging with their target demographics.

Socio-economic consequences

The departure of Meta from the Russian market has instigated a series of socio-economic consequences, particularly affected the realm of digital advertising and altered consumer behavior and brand perception. This exit has prompted a significant reevaluation of the digital advertising landscape in Russia, leading to a redistribution of advertising budgets.

According to a study by Genius Group and Sostav, in 2022, advertising budgets from YouTube were most often reallocated to VK Advertising, programmatic platforms (automated online ad purchasing), Yandex.Direct video ads, and online cinemas [11]. The most popular alternative to Google AdWords became Yandex.Direct. Budgets from Instagram were most often directed to VK Advertising. Facebook and TikTok were also frequently replaced by VK's advertising products. However, some respondents noted a preference not to redistribute budgets initially intended for foreign advertising platforms at all. The highest share of such responses (over 50%) was noted regarding TikTok, with less than 5% of respondents reallocating advertising investments to the alternative service Yappy. The study involved 102 employees from advertising agencies and brands, including Nestle, X5, Splat, Hoff, and Gedeon Richter Pharma.

In response to Meta's departure from the Russian market, companies have been compelled to adapt the

content of their advertising campaigns to align with new platforms. This shift necessitates a reevaluation of content strategies to ensure they resonate with the audiences specific to these alternative platforms, such as VKontakte (VK), Telegram, and Yandex.Direct. Advertisers are now tailoring their messages, visuals, and overall campaign narratives to cater to the unique user behaviors, preferences, and functionalities offered by these services. For instance, VK's community-centric model requires content that fosters engagement and interaction within groups and public pages, while Telegram's focus on channels and bots demands a more direct and personalized communication strategy. Similarly, advertising on Yandex.Direct, which is deeply integrated with Russia's leading search engine, requires a keen understanding of search intent and user queries to craft effective search ads. This adaptation process not only showcases the versatility and creativity of marketers but also underscores the evolving nature of digital advertising, where content must continually evolve to meet the demands of diverse platforms and their respective audiences.

Conclusion

Meta's exit from Russia has catalyzed a period of significant transformation in the advertising market, prompting businesses to reevaluate and innovate their digital marketing approaches. As companies continue to adapt to this new reality, the evolving landscape presents an opportunity for growth, learning, and the development of a more diversified and robust digital advertising ecosystem within Russia. This period of transition underscores the adaptability of advertisers and the enduring importance of digital marketing in connecting brands with their audiences, even amidst changing technological and geopolitical landscapes.

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